

Incidence of endometrial cancer and its contributing factors among the women attending the Maternity and Child hospital(MCH) of Al Ahsa for abnormal uterine bleeding, A chart review study (2015-2020)

Fatmah Basim Bin Alshaykh MD ¹, Amjed Wahab Alquraini MD ², Gofran mohammed albraheem ³, Zahra Wasel Al Ismael, ³ Shaheen Fatima, MD ⁴

¹Consultant, Obstetrics and Gynecology :King faisal Hospital, Al Ahsa, ² Consultant Obstetrics and Gynecology ,MCH, Al Ahsa , ³Resident obstetrics and gynecology , MCH, Al Ahsa , ⁴Assistant professor , Internal Medicin , Emory University School of Medicine , Atlanta, Georgia, USA .

Corresponding author: Fatimah Basin Bin Al shaykh, Consultant, Obstetrics and Gynecology :King faisal Hospital, Al Ahsa.

Abstract:

Background:

Endometrial cancer is considered as the most frequent gynecological cancer commonly affecting the post-menopausal women. Statistics suggest that worldwide incidence of endometrial cancer has increased in the recent past. The main risk factors of developing endometrial cancer among the premenopausal women include obesity, nulliparity, diabetes mellitus, unopposed estrogen therapy, tamoxifen therapy, and use of sequential oral contraception. The present study was conducted to determine the incidence of endometrial cancer and risk factors associated with it among the women attending the MCH Hospital , Al ahsa, Saudi Arabia.

Material and methods:

It was a cross sectional restrospective chart review study in which data were collected during the 5 years' time of January 2015 to January 2020 from the files of all the cases attended for endometrial biopsy. The data were collected in the data collection form specially designed for this study. Which consisted of the demographic characteristics of

the study subjects (such as age, BMI, Gravida, Parity, presence of infertility or not, presence of amenorrhea or not and family history of endometrial cancer) , the information on the symptoms for which the subjects underwent for endometrial biopsy and possible factors (use of any contraceptive , if yes then which type of contraceptive and duration of the use of contraceptives) and the detailed histopathological report of the endometrial tissue. The data were entered and analyzed by using the SPSS,version 21. Chi Square tests (χ^2) were done to test for the association and/or the difference between two categorical variables were applied. A p-value equal to or less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression analysis was done to determine the Odds Ratio.

Results:

A total of 119 patients attended MCH during the January 2015 to January 2020 for suspected endometrial cancer. The mean age of the patient was 48.94 years \pm Std. dev. 6.90 years . The vast majority of the patients (89.1%) attended with the complain of abnormal uterine bleeding while almost eleven percent (10.9%) attended for pelvic or abdominal pain. Eighteen out of 119 histopathological reports showed confirmed endometrial cancer making an incidence rate to be 15.1%. Logistic regression analysis showed Adjusted Odd Ratio for the Age group (AOR 3.00, 95% CI 1.95-5.85), higher gravida (AOR, 1.51, 95% CI 0.51–1.84), Nulliparity (AOR 6.2, 95% CI 2.84-13.56), Family history of endometrial cancer (AOR 6.6, 95% CI 4.14-12.9), Amenorrhea (AOR 1.60, 95% CI 1.40–1.84) and Hypertension (AOR 1.30, 95% CI 1.02–1.54).

Conclusion:

The present study has shown that the incidence of endometrial carcinoma among the patients attending the MCH hospital is very high. Scheduling the screening programme is crucial to identify endometrial cancer in women with family history of endometrial cancer, nulliparous women, multigravida women, infertile women and those who are on contraceptive pills. Every patient with abnormal uterine bleeding should undergo endometrial biopsy to rule out endometrial carcinoma.

Key words: Endometrial cancer, risk factors, Abnormal uterine bleeding

Introduction:

Endometrial cancer is considered as the most frequent gynecological cancer commonly affecting the post-menopausal women. It is the fourth most common cancer among women in United States. [1] Statistics suggest that worldwide incidence of endometrial cancer has increased in the recent past. The study showed that rates of endometrial carcinoma of uterus was highest in North America and Europe and lowest in middle income countries such as India and South Africa. [2] According to one meta-analysis the pooled risk of endometrial cancer among women with postmenopausal abnormal uterine bleeding was 9% (95% CI, 8%-11%) . [3]

Though endometrial carcinoma is more prevalent among the post-menopausal women but women less than 40 years are not immune to it. According to one estimate 10% of the women suffer from endometrial cancer before menopause. Abnormal uterine bleeding, the main symptom of possible endometrial cancer, among postmenopausal women requires endometrial histopathological examination. However, among premenopausal women, the abnormal uterine bleeding is quite common and causes are mainly non-cancerous. The indication to seek endometrial cancer among these age groups are not clear. However it is advisable for premenopausal women with abnormal

uterine bleeding with associated cancer risk factors to go for D&C and histopathological examination .^[4]

Excess estrogen exposure is predominantly responsible for the development of endometrial cancer. The excess estrogen produces continued stimulation of the endometrial lining which causes endometrial hyperplasia and probably endometrial cancer. The main risk factors of developing endometrial cancer among the premenopausal women include obesity, nulliparity, diabetes mellitus, unopposed estrogen therapy, tamoxifen therapy, and use of sequential oral contraception.

Nulliparity, early age of menarche and a history of anovulatory cycles have been established as the risk factors for endometrial cancer among premenopausal women by various cohort studies also.^[5,6] According to one estimate high BMI was responsible for 60% of endometrial cancer cases across the Europe.^[7] Similarly estimated 57% of endometrial cancers in the United States is related to overweight and obesity.^[8] Hormonal factors are strongly associated with development of endometrial cancer. It has been demonstrated that a woman who has given at least one birth during her lifetime has a lower risk of developing endometrial cancer. This might be due to hormonal balance shifts toward more progesterone during pregnancy .^[9] On the contrary women who have never been pregnant and are infertile are also at higher risk of developing endometrial cancer. This is the reason that using combined oral contraceptive pill is associated with a significant reduction in endometrial cancer risk due to suppression of endogenous estrogen levels and increased exposure to progesterone throughout the menstrual cycle .^[10] Many studies suggest polycystic ovary syndrome to be one factor in the pathogenesis of endometrial cancer and this might be due to higher endrogen and estrogen level and lower progesterone levels .^[11] Various researches have been done all over the world to know the risk factors of developing endometrial cancers among the premenopausal women. In a systematic review study ME Pennant et al has found that 0.33% (95% CI 0.23–0.48%,) of the premopausal women with abnormal uterine

bleeding were at risk of developing endometrial cancer.^[12] This review has suggested that risk of developing endometrial cancer was lower in women with heavy menstruation bleeding (OD ratio 0.11%, 95% CI 0.04-0.32) as compared with intermenstrual bleeding (OD ratio 0.52%, 95% CI 0.23-1.16%).^[13] In a Danish case control study the researchers have found women with family history (Odds ratio 2.1, 95% CI 1.1-3.8). Women who received hormone replacement therapy for 1 to 5 years (ODD Ratio 3.1, 95% CI 1.4-7.0). On the other side completion of 1 term pregnancy (Odds ratio 0.6, 95% CI 0.3-1.1), increasing age at first birth and with the number of induced abortions were found to be the factors in decreasing the risk of endometrial cancer. In this review BMI was not demonstrated independent risk factor.^[14] Suzanna Hutt et al in his study has found that BMI was the greatest risk factor. The BMI of 25 or over gave an increased risk of 2.01%, a BMI of 30 or over gave an increase of 5.24%, and a BMI of 40 or over led to an increase of 6.9%. Polycystic ovary syndrome in this study was the second highest increased risk at 4.2%. Diabetes, null parity and non continuous HRT were also significant increased risk factors.^[15] The present study was conducted to determine the incidence rate of endometrial cancer and the risk factors associated with it among the patients attending the Maternity and Child hospital, Al Ahsa for abnormal uterine bleeding.

Materials and Methods:

It was a cross sectional retrospective chart review study in which data were collected during the 5 years' time of January 2015 to January 2020 from the files of all the cases attended for endometrial biopsy at Maternity and child health Care hospital, Al Ahsa, Saudi Arabia. All the patients attending the outpatients' clinics of the hospital for abnormal uterine bleeding and subjected for histopathological examinations of uterine tissue for the detection of endometrial cancer in a specific time period was the study population. The inclusion criteria was all the premenopausal and post-menopausal women undergoing histopathological examination for endometrial cancer. The total number of women attending the hospital with the possible endometrial cancer and

subjected to endometrial biopsy during last five years was approximately 600. According to previous study the prevalence of 10% of the endometrial cancer among women with abnormal uterine bleeding was noted. The sample size was calculated using a Fisher's formula by cited by Mugenda & Mugenda (1999)^[16]; $n = Z^2pq / e^2$ where n = the desired sample size, Z = the standard normal deviate at 95% confidence level (1.96), P = the estimated proportion of the target population, 18% of whom may be suffering from endometrial cancer documented by SEER cancer statistics review for Asian country (Howlander, N., et al. SEER Cancer Statistics Review, 1975-2008. 2011), $q = 1-p$, e = desired level of precision (0.05). So the calculated study sample was $n = (1.96)^2(0.18)(0.82)/(0.05)^2 = 226$. Since the target population was less than 10,000, and finite in nature; A final sample estimate will be calculated using the formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size and n_0 is the calculated sample size for infinite population. $n = 226 / 1 + (226-1)/600 = 165$ participants. A ten percent of the calculated sample size was added to cater for non-response which will make it 181 subjects. The sampling was done by the convenience sampling, the most common method. We selected the suitable cases over period between January 2015 and January 2020. The data were collected in the data collection form specially designed for this study. Section 1 consisted of the demographic characteristics of the study subjects (such as age, BMI, Gravida, Parity, presence of infertility or not, presence of amenorrhea or not and family history of endometrial cancer). The section 2 collected the information on the symptoms for which the subjects underwent for endometrial biopsy and possible factors (use of any

contraceptive, if yes then which type of contraceptive and duration of the use of contraceptives) and section 3 contained the detailed histopathological report of the endometrial tissue. The data were entered and analyzed by using the statistical package for social sciences, version 21 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics were presented using counts, proportions (%), mean \pm standard deviation whenever appropriate. Descriptive statistics (e.g. number, percentage) and analytic statistics using Chi Square tests (χ^2) to test for the association and/or the difference between two categorical variables were applied. A p-value cut off point of 0.05 at 95% CI was used to determine statistical significance. Logistic regression analysis was done to determine the OR. An approval letter from the research committee of the MCH hospital was taken before starting the research. Consent was also taken from each participant of the study.

Results:

Socio demographic characteristics:

A total of 119 patients attended MCH during the January 2015 to January 2020 for suspected endometrial cancer making the response rate of 65%. The mean age of the patient was 48.94 years \pm Std. dev. 6.90 (Range :35-71 years). The majority of the patients (65.5%) were in the age group of 41-50 years followed by the patients who were in the age group of 51-60 years (24.4%) while minority of the patients were in the age group of 31-40 years (4.2%) and > 60 years age group (5.9%). The majority of the patients were obese (58.0%) while 36.6% were overweight and only 8.4% were of normal weight. The mean gravida of the participants was 6.21 \pm Std. Dev. 2.94 (Range: 0-14). More than half of the patients were (52.9%) were 6-10 gravida followed by 37.8% of the patients who were either non gravida or up to 5 gravida. Only 9.2% of the patients were more than 11 gravida. The mean parity of the patients was 5.15 \pm Std. Dev. 2.56 (Range: 0-11). Only 6.7% of the patients were nulliparous while 53.8%, 38.7% and 0.8% were having 1- 5

children , 6-10 children and > 11 children respectively. Only 4 patients (3.4%) were infertile. Almost eighteen percent of the patients (17.6%) were suffering from amenorrhea. Around thirty eight percent (N=45) of the patients were suffering from type 2 diabetes while 22.7% were suffering from hypertension. Only 13.4% of the patients had family history of endometrial cancer. Almost 17% of the patients were using contraceptive. Thirty five percent of the patients were using estrogen pills while 45% were using Progesterone pills and 10% each were using combined and other methods. The detailed clinic demographic characteristics of the patients are shown in table 1 .

Table 1: Showing the clinico demographic characteristics of the patients

Variables	Number	Percentage
Age: 48.94 ± Std. dev. 6.90 (35-71 years)		
Age groups:		
31-40 years	5	4.2
41-50 years	78	65.5
51-60 years	29	24.4
>61 years	7	5.9
BMI		
Underweight	0	0
Normal weight	10	8.4
Overweight	40	33.6
Obese	69	58.0
Mean gravida : 6.21 ± Std. Dev. 2.94 (Range :0-14)		

0-5 gravida	45	37.8
6-10 gravida	63	52.9
>10 gravida	11	9.2
Parity: Mean parity: 5.15 ± Std. Dev. 2.56 (Range: 0-11)		
Nulliparous	8	6.7
1-5 parous	64	53.8
6-10 parous	46	38.7
>11 parous	1	0.8
Fertility status		
Fertile	115	96.64
Infertile	4	3.36
Amenorrhea		
Yes	21	17.6
No	98	82.4
Family history of endometrial cancer		
Yes	16	13.4
no	103	86.6
Chronic disease		
No chronic disease	47	39.5
Diabetes	45	35.8
Hypertension	27	22.7
Use of contraception		
Yes	20	16.8

No	99	83.2
If yes then which (N=20) contraceptive		
Estrogen	7	35
Progesterone	2	10
Both	9	45
Other method	2	10

Clinico pathological characteristics:

The vast majority of the patients (89.1%) attended the emergency clinic with the complain of abnormal uterine bleeding while almost eleven percent (10.9%) attended for pelvic or abdominal pain. Eighteen reports out of 119 histopathological reports showed confirmed endometrial cancer making an incidence rate to be 15.1%.Endometrial hyperplasia was detected among the 11.8% of the cases while 87% of the patients sample did not show any evidence of endometrial cancer on histopathological examination. The details of the histopathological examination result are shown in table 2.

Table 2; Showing the histopathological result of the endometrium of the patients

Variables	No.	%
Clinical presentation		
Abnormal uterine bleeding	106	89.1
Pelvic or abdominal pain	13	10.9
Histopathological exam report		
No cancer detected	87	73.1
Endometrial hyperplasia	14	11.8
Endometrial cancer detected	18	15.1

Detected endometrial cancer		
Localized and non-invasive	21	87.5
Locally invasive	3	12.5

Association of clinico demographic characteristics with the incidence of endometrium cancer:

The endometrial cancer was significantly more prevalent among the age group of > 60 years of the patients than those in the age group of 51-60 years, 41-50 years and 31-40 years age group (71.43% vs. 6.89% vs.11.54 vs.40%,P=0.001). BMI did not have any significant association with endometrium cancer incidence. Patients with >10 gravida were suffering from endometrial cancer significantly more that those with 0-5 and 6-10 gravida (63.64% vs.13.35 % vs.7.94%, P=0.001). Parity of the patients did not have significantly associated with the presence of endometrial cancer. (P=0.578). Similarly sterility status of the patient did not have significant relationship with the incidence of endometrial cancer (P= 0.285).Endometrial cancer was more among the patients with amenorrhea than those without amenorrhea which was statistically significant (33.34% vs. 17.35%, P=0.027). Incidence of endometrial cancer was significantly more among the patients with family history of endometrial cancer than those whose did have the family history of endometrial cancer (50% vs. 9.71%, P=0.000).

Logistic regression analysis:

Logistic regression analysis showed Adjusted Odd Ratio for the Age group (AOR 3.00, 95% CI 1.95-5.85), higher gravida (AOR, 1.51, 95% CI 0.51–1.84), Nulliparity (AOR 6.2, 95% CI 2.84-13.56), Family history of endometrial cancer (AOR 6.6, 95% CI 4.14-12.9), Amenorrhea (AOR 1.60,95% CI 1.40–1.84) and Hypertension(AOR 1.30, 95% CI 1.02–

1.54) The details of the association of endometrial cancer with the demographic characteristics are shown in table 3.

Table 3: showing the association of clinico demographic characteristics with the incidence of endometrial cancer.

Variables	No endometrial cancer No.(%)	Endometrial hyperplasia No.(%)	Endometrial cancer confirmed No.(%)	OR	95% CI	P Value
Age group				3,0	1.95-5.85	0.001
31-40 years	3(60.0)	0(0.00)	2(40.0)			
41-50 years	59 (75.64)	10 (12.82)	9 (11.54)			
51-60 years	24(82.76)	3 (10.35)	2(6.89)			
>61 years	1(14.28)	1(14.29)	5 (71.43)			
BMI						0.110
Underweight	0	0	0			
Normal weight	6 (50.0)	2(16.67)	4(33.33)			
Overweight	29(72.5)	7(17.5)	4(10.00)			
Obese	52(75.36)	7(10.14)	10(14.50)			
Gravida				1.51	0.51–1.84	0.001
0-5 gravida	36(80.0)	3(6.65)	6(13.35)			
6-10 gravida	48(76.19)	10(15.87)	5(7.94)			
>10 gravida	3(27.27)	1(9.09)	7(63.64)			
Parity				6.22	2.84-13.56	0.004
Nulliparous	6(62.5)	0(0.00)	1(37.5)			
Multiparous	81(72.32)	14(12.50)	17(15.18)			

Family history of endometrial cancer				6.6	4.14-12.9	0.000
Yes	7(43.75)	1(6.25)	8(50.0)			
No	80 (77.67)	13(12.62)	10(9.71)			
Fertility status						0.285
Fertile	2(50.0)	0(0.00)	2(50.00)			
Infertile	85 (68.70)	14(12.17)	16(19.13)			
Amenorrhea				1.60	1.40–1.84	0.027
Yes	11(52.38)	3(14.28)	7(33.34)			
No	76(71.43)	11(11.22)	11(17.35)			
Chronic disease				1.30	1.02–1.54	0.005
No chronic disease	41(87.23)	4(8.51)	2(4.26)			
Diabetes	35(75.56)	6(13.33)	4(11.11)			
Hypertension	11(40.74)	4(14.81)	12(44.45)			
Use of contraception				1.69	1.15-2.49	0.016
Yes	10(50.00)	3(15.00)	7(35.0)			
No	77(77.78)	11(11.11)	11(11.11)			
If yes then which (N=20) contraceptive				1.64	1.10-2.48	0.000
Estrogen	7 (100.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)			
Progesterone	2(100.0)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)			
Both	0(0.00)	3(33.33)	6(66.67)			
Other method	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	2(100.0)			

Discussion:

The present study was an attempt to determine the incidence of endometrial cancer and its contributing factors among the patients attending the MCH hospital with the suspected signs of endometrial cancer. The study has found a high incidence endometrial cancer among them during January 2015 to January 2020 .The incidence rate among the women attending the MCH hospital with the suspected sign of endometrial cancer was 15.1% .In a similar Pakistani study an incidence of 5.2% of endometrial cancer was reported among the patients attending the hospital with the symptoms of Abnormal Uterine bleeding .^[17] One indian study examining endometrial pathology on patients with abnormal Uterine Bleeding has shown that 4.4% of the patients had endometrial carcinoma.^[18] A study on endometrial cancer Incidence trends in Europe consisting of 13 countries has shown that incidence of endometrial cancer ranged from >40 per 100,000 in Slovakia and the Czech Republic to <30 per 100,000 in France, Spain, and the United Kingdom. Rates were lowest in the United Kingdom (23 per 100,000).^[19] In a yet other global study done between years 2006- year 2007 the researchers have found the rates of endometrial cancer varied 10 fold across countries. The highest rates were reported from North America, Eastern and Northern Europe. USA and Slovakia showed 19 cases per 100 000 while the South Africa and India showed 1%, and 3%, respectively.^[20] The incidence of endometrial cancer was highest (71.43%) in the age group of patients with more than 61 years in our study. In the USA study also higher age (60-64 years) was reported as an important risk factor (OR 7.95, 95% CI 3.26-19.37) for endometrial cancer.^[21] In the present study a higher incidence of endometrial cancer was also detected in the age group of 31-50 years (51.54%). In a meta analysis suggested that age at menopause was positively associated with endometrial cancer. In this analysis the pooled RR of endometrial cancer for the

highest versus the lowest age at menopause was found to be 1.89 (95%CI: 1.58-2.26).^[22] Srilankan study has also shown that women with age > 55 years were at more risk of developing endometrial cancer. (AOR = 4.69; 95% CI:2.16-10.2) .^[23] Parity did not play any role as the risk factor for endometrial cancer in the present study (P=0.594). However one literature review has found that Parity reduced risk of disease (RR 0.66, CI 0.60–0.74).^[24] An analysis of epidemiological studies has shown that there was a significant inverse association between parity and risk of developing endometrial cancer for parous versus nulliparous (0.69, 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.65-0.74; I(2) = 76.9%). It has been found in this study that Risk ratio decreased when the number of parity increased.^[25] Family history of endometrial cancer was strongly associated with the increased incidence of endometrium cancer in the present study. [Linda S Cook](#) et al have also reported that first or second degree family history of uterine cancer was modestly associated with the risk for overall endometrial cancer odds ratio (OR), 1.3; 95% CI, 0.9-1.9).^[25] One more study has reported endometrial cancer in first or second degree relative was associated with significantly increased risk of endometrial cancer (P=3.8×10⁻⁷).^[26] The Danish case control study has also reported that family history of endometrial cancer had an odds ratio for endometrial cancer of 2.1 (95% CI , 1.1-3.8).^[28] One Srilankan study has reported that the independent risk factor of endometrial cancer was family history of any type of cancer among the first degree relative (AOR = 12.6; 95% CI:5.14-30.9).^[23] Endometrial cancer was significantly more among the nulliparous women than that of multiparous women in the present study .The same result was published in a hospital based case control study in Iran where the OR of developing endometrial cancer among the nulliparous women was 6.23 , 95% CI 2.86-13.39).^[29] One evidence based study published by Lancet has concluded that the the risk of nulliparity was related to the

increased number of ovulatory cycles .^[29] Infertility was detected as a risk factor in the Iranian study (OR 2.38 , 95% CI -1.32-4.31) and Srilankan study (AOR = 3.84; 95% CI:1.37-10.7).^[30] However in the present study infertility was not significantly associated with the incidence of endometrial cancer. Hypertension was significantly associated with increased incidence of endometrial cancer in the present study. The same result was obtained by Zhao, J et al in his study on chinese population which found that hypertension had OR of 2.725 , 95% CI 1.108-3.431 for developing endometrial cancer.^[31] A systematic review and meta-analysis of case-control and cohort studies on the association of hypertension with endometrial cancer has shown an increased risk of endometrial cancer with hypertension (AOR 1.61 ,95% CI 1.41-1.85 for all studies).^[32] The obesity was associated with the increased incidence of endometrial cancer in many studies. [Maryam Ghanbari Andarieh](#) et al has found OR of 1.71 among the patients with BMI ≥ 25 for developing endometrial cancer.^[29] The srilankan study has also reported a strong association of obesity with the endometrial cancer.^[22] In this study BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² had adjusted AOR of 11.85 towards developing endometrial cancer. Zhao, J et al has found among the chinese population that BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² was significantly associated with the increased incidence of endometrial cancer (OR 2.705, 95% CI 1.121–3.889).^[31] However in the present study we did not find any association between obesity and endometrial cancer (P=0.110). The present study showed that the other methods of contraception was significantly associated with increased incidence of endometrial cancer .The oral contraceptive played protective effect on the incidence of endometrial cancer. Many studies have published the protective action of oral contraceptive in long run. [S S Jick](#) et al reported in their case and control study that adjusted RR for ever user to never user was 0.48 (95% CI, 0.26-0.89) for developing endometrial carcinoma.^[33]

Conclusion:

The present study has shown that the incidence of endometrial carcinoma among the patients attending the MCH hospital is very high. Scheduling the screening programme is crucial to identify endometrial cancer in women with family history of endometrial cancer, nulliparous women, multigravida women, infertile women and those who are on contraceptive pills. Every patient with abnormal uterine bleeding should undergo endometrial biopsy to rule out endometrial carcinoma.

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